

ISic0773

I.Sicily inscription 0773

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

volcanic (local)

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Found in the castle in demolition material

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 12341

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 16.5-19 cm

Width 69.8 cm

Depth 23.8 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 100 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. [---Au]gusti et(vac.undefined)

2. [---]

Apparatus

Text of I.Lipara

Translation

Commentary

It is assumed the text continued on a second block, probably below (now lost). Manganaro would restore as "Genio Augusti et Ti. Caesaris d.d.", following CIL 10.7340 and a text known only from Gualtherus (Messana, 1624), p.53, n.356.

Digital identifiers:

TM 493957

EDR 158477

EDCS 32701116

PHI 334857

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 749

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 191-192 no.83 fig.89

Bernabò Brea, L, Cavalier, M 1998. Meligunìs Lipára IX. Topografia di Lipari in età greca e romana. Palermo. At vol.1, p.150 no.25 tav.63.3

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